

TEACHING MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

Pulatova Dilsuz Yusup qizi

Shahrisabz city of Kashkadarya region

3rd school English teacher

***Abstract:** This article explores the issues of using modern technologies of the global Internet, as well as their interaction with traditional methods in the process of learning and teaching foreign languages.*

***Key words:** ICT, and a foreign language, interactive learning, multimedia tools.*

The 21st century is a turbulent time characterized by unprecedented global changes and transformations. The achievements of science and the development of technologies every year acquire more perfect forms, giving a new impetus to thought processes as new opportunities and means appear for transforming and connecting the external awareness of the surrounding reality with the internal processes of mental activity. As we enter the age of digital and information and communication technologies, we are faced with tasks of a kind that we have never encountered before. School and university teachers around the world are trying to keep up with technical and technological progress, but in order to prepare students for life in the 21st century, it is necessary to reconsider the entire education system as a whole, and take a fresh look at teaching methods.

At the present stage of technology development, all interactive methods for optimizing the assimilation of material in the process of teaching foreign languages can be classified according to the way they are introduced into the educational process and according to the goals that need to be achieved when using a particular method. The practical use of interactive methods that can be applied in the process of teaching foreign languages can be divided into two groups:

- working offline, that is, not requiring a connection to the global Internet: interactive whiteboards and CDs
- working online, that is, requiring connection to the global Internet: network resources in the form of various educational and developmental exercises, games, images, videos on the websites of well-known publishers and organizations (Cambridge, Oxford, Macmillan, British Council, etc.), and interactive test systems.

These funds undoubtedly mark a qualitatively new stage in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. So, let's consider each of the above multimedia tools and technologies separately. At the moment, more and more foreign language teachers use in their work, in addition to traditional methods and techniques, countless innovations offered by the world of computer technology, and, in particular, interactive whiteboards. But what exactly are interactive whiteboards? There are two types of such multimedia tools: virtual and real interactive whiteboards. A virtual whiteboard is a regular chalkboard placed on a computer monitor, which helps students in the online space of a class or audience to see everything that the teacher writes or depicts on the screen. Such a whiteboard is also called an electronic whiteboard, it is usually used at conferences, presentations or in data sharing systems when organizing audio and video contacts between two or more participants using programs such as Microsoft NetMeeting, Microsoft

Office Live Meeting. A real interactive whiteboard is seen as a large monitor panel that combines the functions of an ordinary chalkboard, a projector screen, an electronic copy of the whiteboard and a computer touch monitor. In turn, real interactive whiteboards are divided into four subspecies, depending on the technologies used: resistive (touch), electromagnetic, ultrasonic (infrared) and laser⁶⁸. The capabilities of these interactive whiteboards allow you to create a wide range of educational programs that become indispensable for both teachers and students in the process of studying foreign language material. Today, there are a wide variety of companies involved in the development of such multimedia tools: Smart Technologies, Egan TeamBoard, GTCO CalComp, Promethean, ReturnStar, PolyVision, Hitachi, Panasonic, Interactive Technologies, etc., and the most common software for boards of this kind today remains Microsoft Office Word and PowerPoint.

In recent years, a significant number of interactive CDs have appeared, both stand-alone, containing programs, dictionaries and foreign language courses, and included in modern educational and methodological complexes in the form of supplements to the "Book for the teacher", "Book for the student" and "Workbook". The multimedia basis of educational CDs allows presenting the studied material simultaneously in text, graphic, sound and visual forms. In the process of combining various audiovisual sources of information in an emotional-figurative context, various types of memory and thinking are activated, increasing the overall effectiveness and efficiency of mastering the studied material. Modeling of communicative situations with the help of certain programs on disks immerses students in the socio-cultural atmosphere of foreign language communication. Interactive CDs act as excellent media for disseminating the necessary information and at the same time do not require connection to the global

Internet, providing the ability to view data anywhere and anytime. Such electronic learning tools can be used as additional material in foreign language classes when consolidating and monitoring the acquired knowledge and skills, programs for self-education, as well as to avoid problems of "lag" among students absent from classes.

So, we can conclude that in the age of computer technology and the heyday of the global Internet, it is very important to find the right and optimal combination, ratio, the golden mean between interactive, multimedia tools and technologies of the global Internet and traditional methods of teaching foreign languages in order to create favorable conditions for students, influencing the formation and maintenance of their motivation to learn a foreign language and to reveal, expand students' opportunities to work with information, which contributes to the development of their innovative thinking, enhances the desire for collective learning in cooperation, forms language and communicative competence.

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